

Archive Architectures

Transmedial Publishing Interfaces for Open Learning Systems

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"We are witnessing a structural transformation of the technical object. It is now dispersed into multilayered network infrastructures, its constituent elements endowed with forms of agency not yet easily comprehended, its constitution governed by a multitude of protocols and standards. This essay explores the extent to which the book can serve as paradigmatic example of this transformation."

We are witnessing a structural transformation of the technical object. It is now dispersed into multilayered network infrastructures, its constituent elements endowed with forms of agency not yet easily comprehended, its constitution governed by a multitude of protocols and standards. This essay explores the extent to which the book can serve as paradigmatic example of this transformation. Today, the book operates as a node in logistical networks, as a source of big data strategies in new economies of capture, as a sensation surface involved in formatting attention, as a key relay in semiotic capitalism, and as educational resource whose status as core element in open learning systems has been both enhanced and challenged by dynamic publishing. As technologies such as print-on-demand, object-oriented databases, and virtualized computing have matured to the point that a poly-medial architecture is sustainable despite inevitable hard and software anachronization, it is this architecture that is key to our vision of the book.

Comprehending the book as a distributed dynamic rather than a stable object challenges numerous methodological and technological assumptions that have guided and governed book production in the past. The design-based process of exploration we outline here is organized as an iterative process that oscillates between analytical engagements and the development of software tools. Given our interest in relating the structural transformation of the book to processes of institutional transformation and the logistical organization of new knowledge ecologies, the essay is both conceptual and practice-based to explore the various registers of the becoming-immanent of the book in our modes of communicative relation (Rossiter & Zehle 2015c).

Part of what makes a publishing platform like *Scalar* attractive to us is that it can accommodate the polyvocal actuality of our research. Despite frequent invocations of the pleasures and potentialities of transdisciplinary arts-and-technology research, the organization of such research processes involve a fair amount of translation: of conceptual idioms, of methodologies, of assumptions. While the project has not yet been completed, it has already become clear that a large number of incommensurabilities—things that do not translate—will remain and will have to be accommodated rather than disappear in and through translation. One could even say that it is this remainder that drives the project, a kernel around which we wish to organize our research beyond the faith in all-encompassing humanities frameworks and the solutionism of a technical development process. The focus on a technical development process in the second half of this essay intrigues us not because practice is the telos of theory (it is not). But in the world of network media, standards are sometimes set by intervention on the level of multilateral governance, formal and *de jure*. More often, however, standards are set through the introduction and widespread adoption of a best practice strategy, *de facto*. Not discounting related efforts to operate on the level of multistakeholder governance, it is on this level we wish to intervene through our research. However, the design of our research process includes the creation of an international stakeholder network, many of whose members are already involved in such negotiations.

The modular approach to the writing of this essay reflects the distinctiveness and diversity of disciplinary positions involved. And finally, it reflects our own uncertainty regarding the digital humanities. It is not at all obvious to us that humanities research will or even should be our primary mode of engagement with the future of the book. Maybe the informatization of publishing demands entirely different forms of engagement, driven by new literacies and organized through new research constellations.

Part One: Book Futures

We believe that the academic book of the future will remain a printed volume which can be marked, tagged, loaned and cited interchangeably with existing books. This physical object will, however, be defined completely by an open data structure containing all of the design and materials information necessary for different printers to manufacture identical (or remixed) volumes. In the process, the book will become truly sustainable for the first time. Printers already accept such data and will fulfill orders competitively even for single units, collecting and re-distributing authors' and institutes' revenues as instructed. Taking the iterative development processes of rapid prototyping as a methodological and practical point of departure, we propose to develop a data structure that can be transformed, without loss, as print technologies evolve. It contains a platform-independent description of the book to enable production in other formats such as educational editions, electronic reading devices, online learning systems, or as layers on research repositories, archives, and collections. The primary book structure will also form the root of a potentially large tree of related data objects that are linked to form a sustainable digital repository of ancillary media and supporting information.

The physical book is not merely ornamental, but remains a “means of inquiry in its own right” (Schnapp 2014). It is irreplaceable for simple practical reasons. That said, we also recognize that information essential to modern research can often no longer be encapsulated in a static printed volume alone. Progress in hybrid publishing during the last decade has demonstrated that the academic book must move beyond its inherited and longstanding format. It is essential that the book gain the capacity to reference other media, not simply citing a film but linking directly to a specific time-code when read electronically, launching a simulation with a specific dataset or rendering a game sequence via a game engine (Yamamiya 2009). The book of the future must be able to incorporate citations of all time-based media with the same rigor and facility characteristic of textual citation.

Equally significant, the academic publishing environment is today threatened by hazards unique to the 21st century: material cited in research publications is becoming increasingly aberrant. While print remains a reliable reference, the lifetime even of archives and repositories on the internet, not to mention institutions' websites, is very uncertain. Early media such as television and experimental data are being lost at an alarming rate. The results of many key publications in all fields, from science to archaeology, can no longer be reproduced because of loss of their experimental data due to technical obsolescence and institutional reorganization.

Our vision of the printed book of the future is inspired by Alan Kay's *Dynabook* (Kay 1974). The book as the root of a linked digital repository has become a viable and sustainable reality only during the last five years. We can, of course, still publish books accompanied only by data necessary and sufficient to manufacture the printed volume or to deliver derivatives to electronic platforms; but as a linked digital repository, the book has the capacity also to contain, make accessible, and potentially to preserve, other works and materials.

1. Research Horizon

Read with love, the book, as Deleuze noted, is “a little non-signifying machine, and the only question is ‘Does it work, and how does it work?’” (Deleuze 1969). To reflect on the dispersal of the book into technical networks, we sketch a research horizon that allows us to comprehend not only what the book is, its status as key interface and repository, but what the book does, how it operates, and how changes in the way these operations are organized and related to changes in the way we organize ourselves as authors and readers. To read, Deleuze suggests, is to connect the book to its outsides:

“This intensive way of reading, in contact with what’s outside the book, as a flow meeting other flows, one machine among others, as a series of experiments for each reader in the midst of events that have nothing to do with books, as tearing the book into pieces, getting it to interact with other things, absolutely anything, is reading with love” (ibid.).

This is not the affective pathos of research, it is the acknowledgment that singular acts of reading involve an affective relationship. The way we comprehend the act of reading must attend to the affective registers of our own situatedness in information networks, and to the way this situation not only changes the way we read but involves changes to our capacities for relation that in turn further affect the way we read (Zehle 2015b). What follows are methodological remarks that signal our interest in developing a research framework that both offers a conceptual idiom and organizes a concrete workflow.

One of the reasons why we engage with the question of the book, its status, its uses, and its functionalities in logistical infrastructures, is that the book operates as a scalable interface to a much wider set of research concerns. A historical survey of the multiple cultural, economic, political, and social practices that have contributed to the transformation of the book into a networked object is beyond the scope of this essay. However, we want to at least reference some of the existing proposals we do not wish to pursue, because of their implicit oversights of the complexity of workflow integration, technical limitations, and failings in design methods to identify system requirements. A current example of such proposals are the positions in what can be called ‘*document format battles*’ between Markdown and HTML5. On one side, O’Reilly Media have advocated HTML5 with the project HTMLBook (<https://github.com/oreillymedia/HTMLBook>), on the other side the Digital Publishing Toolkit (<http://networkcultures.org/digitalpublishing/>) has advocated Markdown. In terms of addressing the book as a network object, to focus on a document format alone is misleading, as neither format can cope with fully digitizing the print book, let alone extending the book to new hybrid forms. Instead the

focus should be on requirements for any document markups, ISO standards, and interoperability, as well as technology stacks as opposed to document formats, as this is needed to cope with the complexity of the networked book. In our design approach, any document format can be used as long as it fits the requirements, meaning there is no migration or exclusion of users or workflows on a document format basis.

Making

Developed in the methodological context of 'Digital Humanities 2.0', i.e. the shift from large-scale digitization (DH 1.0) to research that is "deeply generative, creating the environments and tools for producing, curating, and interacting with knowledge that is 'born digital' and lives in various digital contexts" (Schnapp & Presner 3, 10), the proposed project includes a strong focus on making, "making in the poetic sense of poesis, but also in the sense of design carried out in action, the modelling and fabrication of intelligent things, the generative and re-generative aspects of creation and co-creating" (ibid. 8). As 'born digital' audiences access outcomes of academic research beyond disciplinary academic communities, changes in reading also frame the future of the academic book. From within a cross-disciplinary imaginary, the project combines a focus on software development with the historical awareness that the open artistic frameworks of modern and contemporary art already anticipate the reconfigurability of database narratives (Rossiter & Zehle 2015a). The project uses design research methods to implement its practice-based approach and provide a framework for a cross-disciplinary negotiation of the future of 'the book' in terms of both craft and code beyond simple analog and digital dichotomies (Sennett 2008, Anderson 2012). By creating actual prototypes and code-based workflows, with the aim to develop the idea of a 'procedural literacy' further into a comprehension of both the cultural and information-technological logics of how the academic book works as a complex aesthetic object, comprehended (and designed) as computational objects (Bogost 2010, Campanelli 2011, HPC 2013). A design research approach explicitly frames the analytical (and political) issues arising from the transition to a publishing process organized around hybrid objects.

Interfaces

Interface, Alexander Galloway has suggested, is itself a method, and attention to the methodological register of interfaces—its designs, its uses, its processualities—include the analysis of attention itself (Galloway 2012). For Bernard Stiegler, attention operates like an interface: the psychic and social dimensions of our attention already constitute "a kind of interface for what Gilbert Simondon called psychic and collective individuation" (Stiegler 2012). Attention can operate as an interface for individuation because 'the formation of attention in which psychic and collective individuation consists is conditioned by material techniques,' especially the exteriorization (spatialization) of memory: "It is through this external memory, and as this exteriorization that is a socialization and an expression, that attention is able to constitute itself as interface between the psychic and the social" (ibid.). As a consequence, "experience has been technically exteriorized in the form of the technical object" (Stiegler 2012). This process is itself structured, grammatized, "first and foremost [as] a process of making the continuous discrete" whose technologies today aim at "the grammatization of the social relation itself—and through that the capacity to render it industrially discretizable, reproducible, standardizable, calculable and controllable by automata" (ibid.). The infrastructures that structure and sustain our communicative practices are also used to organize the grammatization of social relations, affecting the formation of attention. The rise of computability as a methodological concern, i.e. an interest the operational logics of software-based research processes that affect use (examples: real-time use-dependent retrieval of archival content, digital rights management) require an engagement with software studies methodologies (Berry 2012, Wardrip-Fruin & Mateas 2014) and a data-driven cultural hermeneutics that affects

the production and reception of academic research (Manovich 2013; Hayles 2014). And if we understand publishing as a cultural technique, the expansion of the archival register and the attention paid to a new generation of archive interfaces in publishing is surely one of its most significant contemporary transformations (Zehle 2015a).

Publics

Publishing is intimately tied to the emergence of new (hybrid) publics, and publishing interfaces play a key role in turning issues into “matters of concern” (Latour 2004). As research actors strive to communicate with audiences beyond academic peers, interest grows in new forms of research-based content and corresponding publishing formats that require a restructuring of the academic book to address changes in authorship (single-author vs. real-time collaborative editing and the incorporation of crowd-sourced user-generated metadata and use-dependent retrieval of contents from big data repositories), review (crowd-sourced, peer-to-peer), editing (community-based filtering), status (final vs. permanent beta), structure (modularized to facilitate reuse in other publications and online learning systems), design (cross-platform and responsive layout, social viewing and annotation features, incorporation of real-time information streams), licensing (buy-to-own, buy-to-use, open and public access, fair use provisions for artistic and journalistic uses), distribution (cross-platform, peer-to-peer), and archiving (cloud-based repositories, NoSQL or object-oriented database logics) (CREATE 2014, EIFL 2014). To what extent the separation of academic and journalistic publishing systems makes sense remains to be seen; while developments in journalism remain beyond the scope of the proposed research project, we have followed the growing trend in ‘journalism tech’ and new storytelling platforms.

The proposed project intervenes in the discussion of academic publishing futures (Lambert 2015, Jones & Courant 2014, Suber 2012) with a concrete research proposal. The arguments are about who pays for scholarly publications and publication models to exist, the reader or the author, for example. Also about how institutions can act to address the Open Access agenda, in the case of Harvard introducing a Green Open Access repository in 2008 Digital Access to Scholarship at Harvard ([DASH](#)) and making it mandatory that its academics deposited free copies of their publications. It is concrete because it outlines a specific research path developed in relation to what we perceive to be key trends in dynamic publishing. But it is also concrete in that it focuses discussion on the specific technological protocols and standards whose design in turns affect the scope of individual and collective agency through and within such publishing systems. The focus on transmedia publishing strategies reflects our own interest in the future of publishing as a key register of institutional critique (Alberro & Stimson 2009; Raunig & Ray 2009), a practice of engagement integral to many of the aesthetic practices that have both driven and anticipated the ‘subjective economy’ (Lazzarato 2014) in the context of which the current dispersal of ‘unbound’ (Hall 2013) knowledges occurs. The processes that have freed such ‘unbound’ knowledge are not, of course, limited to the field of knowledge production; but instruments of commoning such as open licensing schemes or piratical distribution networks (Rossier & Zehle 2015b) have a particular relevance to the dynamic of publishing.

2. Part Two: Organizing a Design-Based Research Process

Building on existing cross-disciplinary research, policy, and technical standards, the project addresses three specific transmedia publishing research needs:

1. the creation of a **platform-independent structured document type** for print, transmedia publishing, and object-oriented repository linking;
2. **enhanced transmedia citation and reference management** to address core issues in the shift from print-only to hybrid publishing approaches of academic research, and
3. **collections tools** to allow educators, students and scholars to curate Open Access (OA) and Open Education Resources (OER) content packages.

2.1 Offer a Platform-Independent Structured Document Type

In the shift from print-only to hybrid publishing strategies with faster publishing production cycles, there is a need to ensure texts and images from research outcomes can migrate to new digital forms of the book, to other transmedia formats and open learning systems. These hybrid publishing strategies require the enabling of the semi-automation of part of a dynamic publishing workflow, which includes the following parts of the workflow; typesetting, multi-format conversion, distribution, rights management, file transfer, translation workflows, document updates, payments and reading metrics.

2.1.1 Integrate Workflows

While some document and meta description formats exist, including OASIS, ODT and the W3C and IDPF standards of EPUB3 and HTML5 (eg IDPF, EDUPUB as of 2014, with submissions by Pearson and O'Reilly), VRA, MODS, TEI, they have yet to become an integral part of the working environments, habits, tools, and workflows of academics.

2.1.2 Establish Workflow Compatibility

For such integration, existing work habits of the academic practitioner need to be compared and contrasted with the need for changes in work and use cycles to enable content to be easily purposed in the digital workflow. This project explores how research outcomes across media types can be made digitally compatible by assessing available tools, academic conventions, training and skill levels to map key research processes onto digital publishing workflow.

2.1.3 Provide User Research

Additional studies take extra-academic users of research outcomes into account to develop concrete strategies to facilitate the integration of structured document processes into academic publication life cycles.

2.1.4 Develop Code

Working with industry partners (including Data Futures (UK), Stilo (UK), le-tex (DE), Heidelberg Research Architecture (DE), Sourcefabric (CZ/DE), Fiduswriter (DK, NO), Nätverkstan (SE), EasyDITA (US)) and standards bodies like W3C and IDPF, the project generates software and code to complement and modify available open source solutions.

2.1.5 Develop User Experience Design

A user-oriented interface design is needed to inform users about a) how changes to the document to add structure effects its meaning, b) for screen previews of the multi-format outputs where the target outputs require intervention to preserve the integrity of the publication, especially in multimedia formats.

2.2 Offer Enhanced Transmedia Citation and Reference Management

With the introduction of new media types into the digital book there is a need to specify points in media, a location in run-time or vector position for example, in a video, game sequence, social graph, simulation, calculation or drawing. This amounts to an academic citation and referencing management for transmedia publishing that is backwards-compatible with analog and print media.

2.2.1 Combine Technical and GUI Research

To allow direct links to a specific point in the target media type, a combination of technical and GUI research is needed.

2.2.2 Develop Transmedia Mnemonics

Because transmedia mnemonics do not currently compare with the sophisticated mnemonic and navigational feature of print, neither in terms of features (for example, print cataloging systems, glosses, indexes, running headers, page numbers, tabulation systems, see Vandendorpe 2009, Krajewski 2011) or the organization of parts of a book, style and referencing (MLA, Chicago Manual of Style or Harvard Style do not fully address the layering of computational media), the project proposes methods of mnemonic for use and navigation of transmedia publications. These research tasks focus on key but under-researched areas where new conditions require changes in practitioners' workflows. Framed by two integrative questions and modularized to facilitate research organization, they provide a manageable research focus but open up onto the entire range of digital publishing workflow issues.

2.3 Collections

The term Collections will, in our context of Open Education Resources (OER) and Open Access (OA) publishing, be used to describe the many and increasing ways in which educators and learners can use new digital tools to curate, socially annotate, and author materials into custom collections. Collections can contain text, images, video, annotation, data objects, teaching guides and social media. Collections can be individually authored or collaborative documents. They can also feature a series of new networked measurement and digital asset tracking features known as Learning Resources Analytics (LRA).

It is important to mention that, to work well, Collections are dependent on three Internet design conventions that allow for the easy reuse of content and innovation in tool design: open source, open standards, and open licensing. All of these can be used to translate different philosophies of commoning into concrete technical systems. Like other commons-based approaches, their adoption has been uneven and marked by contradictions.

Contemporary tools and web platforms like [Hackpad](#), [Storify](#) and [Flipboard](#) already possess some of the qualities that Collections should possess, but the latter can go further. In an educational context, specifically, Collections should also allow the integration and facilitation of curriculum design, digital note taking, study and reading groups, digital dissertations, research records and bibliographies.

The Hybrid Publishing Consortium publishing prototypes include the following examples: Merve Remix—in which we digitized the German publisher Merve Verlag’s back catalog of 400 titles (<https://merve.consortium.io/>); Museums and Post-digital Publishing—working with the Swiss museum Fotomuseum Winterthur and the publication *Manifeste!* (<https://github.com/consortium/winterthur-hybrid-publishing-workflow>) in which we examine how the high quality museum catalogue can be digitized and taken into open learning and OER contexts; Traces of McLuhan – a Media Sprint at the Marshall McLuhan Salon, Canadian Embassy, Berlin and the Marshall McLuhan archive, where we created a transmedia trace of a user’s journey through the archive (<https://mcluhan.consortium.io/>).

2.3.1 Open Educational Resources (OER)

The potential of OER to enrich, excite, and inspire learners stands paramount among its positive features, and Collections share in these qualities. However, there are less obvious benefits to their development. For example:

Collections encourage exploratory, adaptive IT policies: University IT systems, along with those in corporations and government, have been developed along a model which allows and effectively builds in high innovation and maintenance costs. However, there is a long-term trend in all these workplaces to work with bring-your-own-device (BYOD) policies. This means people are using any platform or device available to interact with web resources because the institutional systems formally available to them for this purpose have become unworkable. The Collections model is open to the BYOD approach and may be able to help move institutions from their rigid, traditional systems to more flexible IT policies.

Collections are compatible with mixed online learning: there are new types of OER and OA learning environments emerging where Collections can play an important role by forging curated paths through large volumes of material through a mixture of recommendation and semantic data from Learning Resources Analytics.

Collections reduce costs: with or without a financial crisis, crafting educational material and providing teaching is expensive. Moving to new digital environments only adds to that expenditure. The cost-sharing offered by these open ways of working is most likely the only way that the majority of institutions can develop and disseminate their teaching programs in new mixed and distance learning contexts.

2.3.2 Educational media: quality control

Learners’ expectations of online media are being shaped by the commercial-media landscape, which is creating a pressing need for the production quality of educational materials to improve. Collections are key to solving the many problems associated with this challenge. Firstly, by using OER and LRA, Collections allow for a mass of high quality teaching material to be made available at greatly reduced prices. Secondly, by using open source models of collaboration, and by establishing consortia between educational partners, the new tool sets stand to make it significantly easier to publish diverse and large sets of material to new platforms.

2.3.3 Collections tools

Collections technology is no new thing. To some extent, the Collections methodology underpins the whole make-up of the Internet—packet networks and the modularity of information systems—all of which were designed in the 1960s. There are many competing models for organizing information.

Digital Asset Management Systems (DAMS), for example, has been around for decades, but this now represents an outdated model, conceived when networks were not much in use. We now possess models that are more

network oriented, whether they come from the private sector of web development, or from academic research groups or civil liberties activists.

3. Part Three: Technical Plan

3.1 Summary of Digital Outputs and Digital Technologies

There will be four digital outputs for the project. Two are Open Source contributions to the academic community as public infrastructure. The third output will be a series of digital prototype productions of a transmedia publication to demonstrate the research contribution to the field of Open Access and digital publishing. The fourth outcome will be a prototype workflow for the generation of custom OER (in cooperation with the OER team of the Afro-European Mokolo initiative).

3.1.1 Open Source Public Infrastructure

The following software release would look to be compatible with the following example software frameworks. Data Futures (Westminster University), A-machine (Hybrid Publishing Consortium), Scalar (University of Southern California), Booktype and Superdesk (Sourcefabric), Fiduswriter, Transpect (le-tex), Tamboti (Heidelberg Research Architecture) and Superglue.

3.1.2 Enhanced Transmedia Citation and Reference Management

In such citation and reference management, if text is understood in computational terms as a linear string similar to a point in the linear position of the timeline of a video or the trace of a game thread, then these points can be identified, cited, referenced and used in the context of a publication. The design of such a management system is complex, as the fixed properties of print media are no longer the only parameter and the publication becomes more of a recipe for combining a revision point in a variety of distributed media. These features would be explored in a usable Beta prototype software implementation as part of the rapid prototyping research process.

3.1.3 Platform Independent Publication (PIP) Type

This is a software implementation to test the the Platform Independent Publication type, using existing open document standards. Through the project's research, co-creation and design research methods, these standards would be implemented in to facilitate their use by academic practitioners.

3.1.4 Transmedia Publications: Hybrid Publishing Consortium Prototypes

A series of hybrid publications would be released as digital publications, making use of the existing HPC material and context. Some of the digital assets would manifest as hybrid digital print objects via print-on-demand digital printing.

3.2 Hybrid Publishing Consortium, Data Futures and xm:lab—Open Source Publishing Infrastructures

The long term collaboration and objectives of our research network (including HPC, Data Futures, and xm:lab) is to support Open Source infrastructures for transmedia, multi-format, scholarly publishing. Using single

source architectures to output format such as; EPUB, HTML5, ODT, DOCX, PDF, PDF for print-on-demand. The stages in the publishing workflow and life cycle can be described as follows:

1. Document Validation—writing and authoring
2. Document Editing—text, citations, metadata and images
3. Media Editing
4. Layout Design—typesetting and templates; semi-automatic and automatic
5. Publishing
6. Publication Collections—libraries, bookshops, academic and OER repositories
7. Transmedia Publishing API

In this research project we focus on three of these stages: validation, asset management, and a transmedia API.

Major Categories in the Publishing Infrastructure

Archive Architectures – Publishing Infrastructures. Image: © Soenke Zehle, Simon Worthington, Peter Cornwell, Pauline van Mourik Broekman

3.2.2 Platform Independent Publishing (PIP) Standards

The objective of the project is to contribute to the working implementation of an open standards-based, transmedia-structured document, for multi-format publishing. A document-interactive validator will be a valuable tool for use by many document repositories containing unstructured documents that are not usable outside of very limited contexts. HTML5 as opposed to TEI or XML is emerging as the industry standard as an ‘intermediary file format’ with associated metadata and document settings, although this still has many problems such as footnote management. The benefits of machine-readable documents are that users can stay within their preferred writing environment while carrying out validation with the use of an API. The PIP standard allows for a variety of semi-automated processes, known as dynamic publishing—layout, multi-format conversion, distribution, rights management, file transfer, translation workflows, document updates, payments and reading metrics.

3.2.3 Innovations vs. Comparable Open Source Initiatives

Our project is defined by these features: it’s service is not a platform or markup language, and it works via an API so it is more like a feature set to add to other platforms. Points of comparison with other platforms include an interactive validator for platform independent, transmedia document for multi-format publishing; multi-format conversion (by connecting to existing A-machine, multi-format transformation engine); and multi-format design template generation and use. Neither current platforms (Fiduswriter, Booktype, Readthedocs, Sharelatex) nor markups and converters (LaTeX, Pandoc, or the python documentation generator Sphinx) meet all three criteria. The project offers a new publication GUI for transmedia OA and OER content,

interactive inline validation GUI, web real-time updating GUI Javascript Web technologies, and design template libraries for multi-format layouts.

3.2.4 Software Development: Design Research, Working with the Technology Stack

The software development model establishes a three stage process of 'Design Research' for the working group. Firstly, research involves close development with the external open source expert contractors, secondly, testing; thirdly, the running of prototype publication productions as an advanced form of testing. Using this technology stack (validator, assets management and API) provides the design team with structured content and a development environment on which they can then experiment, test, and build templated design layouts for new types of publications. The API model has been chosen as it allows integration with existing open source platforms and encourages user adoption by minimizing workflow disruption caused by platform changes or reskilling.

3.2.5 Validation for Document and Publication Structuring

This task creates a validation system for documents and publication files and asset structuring to have semantic information standardized for multi-format digital publishing, including layout, document structure, output format specific settings, and meta-descriptive information. To make a single source structured document, the validation system gives interactive feedback directly via a GUI (to prompt users to make decisions related to structural markup) or via an API.

3.2.5.1 Interactive Validator

A validator system ensures that the publication workflow structures documents and publication files according to standards and markup requirements that suit single source publishing workflows. As a result of a successful validation process, documents are machine readable and can be used in a variety of semi-automated publishing workflow processes. The validator has to cover different types of structuring that can be customized, including: typesetting (such as headers, bold, superscript, citation styles, line spacing after paragraphs, etc.); semantic document or publication structuring (picture credits, inline quotes, footnotes, pagination, chapters, and section, etc.); media inclusions (images, audio, video, equations, game sequence, etc.); document and publication file type and publication-ready outputs (PRO)-specific settings (image color profiles, print settings, job description files (JDFs), image resolutions, media queries, custom user output format design or content settings); multi-format document settings (i.e. instructions for conversion of a single source document into a specific format that involves information loss, such as a plain text file); a limited set of descriptive metadata (revision history, author, title, date, etc.).

The validator is also required to be interactive with a GUI and to work in an API environment. The interactive feedback is needed because a purely automated validation and structuring process would not be able to make the correct decisions and the files would end up with incorrect formatting. Instead, with an interactive system for user feedback, the user can intervene and make decisions when prompted to do so. Example cases where user feedback is needed divides into two categories. Firstly, workflow processing errors, for example invisible hyperlinks sitting in a document, which can be flagged up for removal in the way that a word processor's 'Navigator' function allows a user to get an overview of a document. Secondly, common user errors, including not correctly marking up unordered lists, or using empty paragraph breaks rather than paragraph styles to make space between paragraphs.

3.2.5.2 Examples of Interactive Structuring Systems

The type of interactive validator we will be developing will be for inline interaction within a web based word processing authoring environment. Here is an example from the commercial product for structured writing called 'EasyDITA': <http://easydita.com/explore/author/>. Other types of interactive validation systems produce a report, for the user to respond to, by editing their document and then resubmitting for further validation. Examples are the International Digital Publishing Forum (IDPF) EPUB Validator (<http://validator.idpf.org/>) and W3C HTML Markup Validation Service (<http://validator.w3.org/>).

Important features of such systems include differentiating between a document and publication, where different structural and metadata requirements are needed. The validation markup and rule set options are: 1. markup set updatable and customizable; 2. heuristics rule sets; 3. centralized or shared markup profiles. Users interact with the validator via the following: 1. GUI; 2. API; 3. command line.

Requirements, Specification and Standards for the Validator. A sample of categories for 'validation' and 'single source' file recipes includes:

- document input types (DOCX, HTML5, ODT, GDoc (subset of ODT));
- publication output types, or what we have termed publication-ready outputs (PROs) that are made up of a combination file type specifications, metadata requirements for the distribution channel, and 'style guides' for editors and designers in creating specific publication components for multi-format publishing. Such components include tables of contents, front cover texts, and back cover texts. A PRO profile is needed per output format as one format will not automatically translate to another format, e.g. a print book to EPUB;
- definition of a single source file, which acts as a container for multiple sources of data, for example different image sizes from an external source for responsive web design, or second external citation, bibliographic and metadata for publishing purposes;
- information for multi-format outputting, design and templating, per output format user tweaks;
- types of media assets that could be included in a document or publication;
- types of structure and semantic information: document layout e.g., H1, bold etc;
- document structure e.g., pagination, chapter etc;
- and metadata fields and standards for a document.

3.2.5.3 Validator Schematic

Archive Architectures – Document Validation. Image: © Soenke Zehle, Simon Worthington, Peter Cornwell, Pauline van Mourik Broekman

3.3 Publication Asset Storage

The publication asset management component of the technology stack will use a MongoDB-based NoSQL infrastructure, which will provide a highly scalable and proven platform for heterogeneous file types together with multiple application programming language bindings. Shared management facilities and efficient use of potentially large numbers of distributed virtual machines makes MongoDB ideal for prototyping and refining a very flexible asset management system. The partners have significant experience in developing loadable javascript-based environments for GUI workflow development with MongoDB, and experience supporting them on major projects with Heidelberg, Princeton, and Westminster University since 2011, as well as providing asset management for several commercial publishing applications. Avoiding off-the-shelf solutions such as Drupal or Wordpress will reduce the project's vulnerability to third party support requirements, will simplify Open Source licensing, and will improve overall sustainability of the framework produced.

An important aspect of the work already conducted by the partners on automated transformation of digital collections is the ability to create and tune metadata exports to multiple XML standards representations, including both MODS and VRA Core4. In addition, a number of workflows already exist to parse asset structures and automate the creation of MongoDB data structures. Together, these sub-components will provide the project with a mature environment for distributed teams of contributors, allowing them to build fully-searchable digital collections of publications' components and create Library of Congress-compliant metadata. The resulting structure can remain as BSON in MongoDB or be exported into other ecosystems such as Tamboti (which uses the native XML eXistdb). Additionally, MongoDB's multiple application programming language bindings enable it to be interfaced rapidly with other components such as Zotero, and allow structured APIs to be implemented for additional project-specific elements of the technology stack.

These tools will be used to build sub-components of the technology stack with the following functionality:

- contributor GUIs controlling decomposition of source documents into individual elements and their integration into a managed collection which can be searched effectively;
- creation of element metadata (using MODS, VRA Core, etc where possible) and editing elements in line, together with version control;
- delivery of versioned publication elements to processing modules;
- output template management, editing and version control;
- interfaces with citation management systems, e.g. Zotero;
- interfaces with other content distribution networks.

3.4 Transmedia Publishing API

An Application Program Interface (API) is the way in which our systems' modular components can communicate with other systems on the internet securely. This means that the functionality we are researching and developing (validation, publication asset structuring, templates) can be integrated into these other systems that we are connecting to. The proposed API allows access to internal modules (Validator, Assets, Design Template Library, and Multi-format Transformer) as well as to external services. Additionally, the use of the API allows the project to use external functionality. For example, link to the software ecosystem called A-machine, with its multi-format transformation software, currently developed by the Hybrid Publishing Consortium. Using the API model of service provision best suits the introduction of solutions to common problems in the Open Access workflow. The API model is one where external features and services like citation management platforms like Zotero and university library distributors such as EBSCO can be integrated. Another benefit of the API model for service distribution is that users can stay within their familiar writing environments. This has the added benefit of encouraging adoption of new services like ours. For these major reasons we see using an API as being the best way to benefit the Open Access community.

3.4.1 Functionality Areas and Use Cases for the API

The API will have four functionality areas:

1. Validation rule set. An external document editing system will be able to have our rule set applied to its documents to raise appropriate flags when a questionable content section is encountered (and to have these flags passed to other systems, and, if appropriate, allow changes and edits to be made to the remote document). The result would be that remote documents could be structured for multi-format conversion.
2. Assets and asset structuring meta description framework. The effect here is that remote systems could store their content on our system, then make use of that content in different ways to, for example, extract all citations or images and captions from an archive and then extract and use these components on a granular level.
3. Templates for authoring and using templates. Templates could be added to the system for use in making multi-format publications using the transformer engine.
4. Transformer. A multi-format conversion engine. After a set of content has been approved by the validator, it could then be sent to the transformer with instructions to use a specific template and be outputted to a number of formats (EPUB, responsive HTML, HTML Book-in-browser, PDF, PDF for print-on-demand [PoD] etc).

The API is used in

- Validation (other systems can have their content structured via use of our API);
- Assets (currently this is for testing purposes, to evaluate how multi-format publications can be stored as a single source master file, which acts as a recipe for its various publication format outputs and can accept different sources to be combined to make these output documents, combining media from different sources. e.g., Pandora, Tamboti and Open Journal System (OJS) etc.);
- Templates (this requires connection to content distribution networks (CDN), so that designers can author templates in software and graphic design libraries they are familiar with, like Bootstrap. The research challenge here for the projects design team is in effect to create modified Bootstrap models for apps, mobile, EPUB etc. Examples would be the open licensed and open source frameworks BakerFramework or PugPig (<http://pugpig.com/>) and famo.us; The CDN model needs to work for template use, too, so that users in another system can check out a template we are creating);
- Transformer multi-format conversion (send files for multi-format conversion to our engine A-machine and receive back the output files).

The system API can connect to the following types of systems: content management systems (CMSs) like Wordpress or Drupal; OA and OER repositories with a digital asset management (DAMS) functionality; any online web based text editor or word processor, for example Fiduswriter software; template repositories such as CDN Bootstrap (<http://getbootstrap.com>) or multi-format format and distribution channels such as the open source app formatting software PugPig (<http://pugpig.com>); third party content services, such as citation management, picture and video repositories such as Zotero, Tamboti or Pandora. The use cases for the API can be varied: book publishing, publication repository, publishing from archives, legacy batch conversion, journal submission processes, web and peer review journals [Open Journal System (OJS)].

3.5 Technical Methodology

At the project's core, we would use co-creation and design research methods to establish the software requirement to address the two central research concerns—transmedia referencing and citation, and document portability. Our research approach includes the following elements:

- **Hybrid Publishing Consortium**—for the project, the context of the existing HPC prototypes provides an experimental framework to keep our research horizon open to extra-academic innovation practices.
- **Rapid Prototyping**—a workable transmedia publishing framework will be established early on to experiment with the incorporation of a wide array of content types in publication prototypes.
- **Discourse Analysis**—focusing on how technology is shaped by the social, methods such as the discourse analysis approach of T-PINC - Technology, Power, Ideology, Normativity and Communication (Koubek, University of Bayreuth), will be employed to better understand the forces acting on technology development.
- **Software Requirements Process**—conventional software methods such as Sommerville's software requirements process will also be employed, with three repeated phases—requirements gathering, specification and validation.
- **Open Source**—design methodologies of open code review will be used. All research publishing will be carried out as Open Access, under Creative Commons Attribution ShareAlike 3.0 license.

3.5.1 Comparative Software Tools Assessment

A comparative assessment of available approaches and open source tools, including:

- **Data Futures**—NoSQL repository migration and long term preservation system. Flexible and custom workflows. <http://www.data-futures.org/>
- **A-machine**—publication multi-format digital conversion, automatic design templating and distribution. Hybrid Publishing Consortium. <http://consortium.io/> and <http://a-machine.net/>
- **Scalar**—multi-media authoring and publishing. <http://scalar.usc.edu/>
- **Public Library**—book scanning and digital librarianship of contemporary reading and books. With connections to Open Library, Archive.org project. <https://openlibrary.org/> and <https://www.memoryoftheworld.org/>
- **Amara, Participatory Culture Foundation**—Crowdsourcing annotation. <http://www.amara.org/>
- **Textus, OKF**—Document annotation. <http://textusproject.org/>
- **Zotero**—citation management, Roy Rosenzweig Center for History and New Media, <http://zotero.org/>

3.5.2 Standards and Formats

For documents OASIS, W3C and IDPF open formats are used. Primarily this will be HTML5 and EPUB3, with attention to emerging EDUPUB W3C and IDPF initiatives announced in a January 2014 W3C call with contributions from publishers Pearson and O'Reilly. <http://www.idpf.org/epub/profiles/edu/>. For citation and referencing purposes this would make use of a combination of Dublin Core (DC), Open Archive Initiative (OAI), and open Citation Style Language (CSL). Additionally, we would use a set of collections and bibliographic management meta description frameworks, Visual Resources Association (VRA) Core 4.0 and Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) from the US Library of Congress and Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) for text.

3.5.3 Hardware and Software

Software used in the project will be MongoDB, Ruby, Transpect from le-tex, Scalar, A-machine framework, Linux, NodeJS, Linux, GitHub. Book scanner from the Public Library project <http://www.ahrc.ac.uk/News-and-Events/Events/Pages/The-Public-Library-Project.aspx>

3.5.4 Data Acquisition, Processing, Analysis and Use

Core data for the project would come from the 'Typemotion' publication and exhibition. Other data would come from partners as well as from stakeholders. Data analysis would be carried out in consultation with industry stakeholders such as Westminster Data Futures project, HPC, Fiduswriter, and le-tex.

3.6 Technical Support and Relevant Experience

Core technical lead comes from the Westminster Data Futures project, HPC, Sourcefabric, Fiduswriter, and le-tex.

3.7 Preservation, Sustainability and Use

3.7.1 Preserving Data

Data Futures specializes in long term data preservation. Data and code would be stored on the Data Futures' distributed and secure long term digital preservation network.

3.7.2 Ensuring Continued Access and Use of Digital Assets

Published material and software code would be published under open licenses. With published materials being in Green Open Access repositories covered by CLOCKSS (Controlled LOCKSS) support. Code would be published on the open repository GitHub and registered with the UK and EU Open Source research repositories. For example: <http://sparceurope.org/resources-repositories/>.

4. Part Four: Technical Objectives

1. Develop a practice-based cross-disciplinary transmedia design and publishing research framework, including the establishment of a stakeholder and knowledge exchange network to facilitate the involvement of a wide variety of users of academic publishing, to address core issues (one related to platform independent publications and the creation of a structured document for print & transmedia publishing, the other related to enhanced transmedia and analogue media citation management) in the transition to transmedia publishing approaches of academic research;
2. Definitively assess platform independent publication file types to ensure texts and images from research outcomes can migrate to new digital forms of the book and other transmedia formats across open learning systems. The project proposes a platform independent document format, based on a compare and contrast analysis of existing formats including OASIS, ODT, and the W3C and IDPF standards of EPUB3 and HTML5 (e.g. IDPF, EDUPUB as of 2014, with submissions by Pearson and O'Reilly);
3. Facilitate research and publishing workflow integration. Because these formats have yet to be integrated into the working environments, habits, tools, and workflows of academics, the project maps research processes (selected via stakeholder and knowledge exchange) onto digital publishing workflows to explore how material across media types can be made digitally compatible, taking into account available tools, academic conventions, training, and skill levels;
4. Provide user research to support workflow analysis and take extra-academic users of research outcomes into account in the development of strategies to facilitate the integration of structured document processes into the academic publication lifecycle with minimal disruption;
5. Develop open source code. Working with industry partners including Data Futures (UK), HPC (EU/US), le-tex (DE), Nätverkstan (SE), and Open Academia Foreningen (NO), and standards bodies like W3C and IDPF, the project produces software and code to complement and modify available open source solutions;
6. Develop user experience design for the document format to inform users about two sets of issues: 1. how changes to the document to add structure effect its meaning, and 2. how to allow previews of the multi-format outputs where the target outputs require intervention to preserve the integrity of the publication;

7. Offer enhanced transmedia citation and reference management to specify points in media (for example in a video, game sequence or social graph) in an academic citation management for transmedia publishing that is backwards-compatible with analogue and print media;
8. Combine technical and GUI research into transmedia hyperlinking in target media types to enhance transmedia citation management;
9. Propose transmedia mnemonics. The technology of print media has complex mnemonic and navigational features. But while style guides exist to help scholars organise their citations and aid the reader to make best use of these references, the layering of computational media onto of print culture has not been addressed in many publication style guides for the Humanities (including MLA, Chicago Manual of Style, or Harvard Style). The project will develop and propose enhanced methods of mnemonics to help the reader use and navigate transmedia publications;
10. Create a prototype platform to demonstrate a transmedia publishing workflow.

These research objectives provide a manageable research focus, yet open up onto the entire range of digital publishing workflow issues, allowing the research project to co-develop additional options for follow-up across stakeholder networks.

5. Part Five: Collaborative Research and Knowledge Exchange

Built on existing collaborations as all consortium members are already involved in relevant networks whose members will be invited as key interlocutors, the research network is designed to complement and amplify the work of a Stakeholder Advisory Group through real-time online and social media exchanges with actors interested in the project, includes online features for remote participation. The peer-to-peer format acknowledges the central role played by informal structures of information exchange in academic research and frames its communication, dissemination and outreach activities.

Suggested members of the research network include: Alliance for Networking Visual Culture; Corridor8; CREATE; Electronic Information for Libraries Network (EIFL); Eurozine; FreeWord Centre (London and Oslo); Hybrid Publishing Consortium; if:book - Institute for the Future of the Book; Institute of Cultural Capital; IT4Arts (WCIT); Leonardo Electronic Almanac (Goldsmiths); metaLAB (Harvard U); Mozilla Foundation; Participatory Culture Foundation; Photomuseum Winthertur; Public Library; Open Library (archive.org); Royal College of Art; SALT Online; Scalar; School of Open, P2P University / Creative Commons; Storyful - Social Media News Agency; Tate Liverpool; Visual Arts in Liverpool, ZKM; The Public School; Mute; Merve Verlag; Nätverkstan; May Day Rooms; Open Syllabus Project; and the Centre for Disruptive Media - Coventry University.

The current research team brings significant expertise to the project in the fields of database architectures, digital publishing, design research, media theory, software development, transmedia narratives, user experience design, and cultural analysis. Given this cross-disciplinary approach, potential academic beneficiaries will be distributed across the disciplinary spectrum; not only those located in traditional (institutional) research settings but also those active across the creative industries, government, media, and civil society, since the transformation of academic publishing affects and involves a wide range of individual and institutional actors with different cultural, economic, political, and technological stakes in the future of the academic book.

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